

Migratory Crossroads Cruise

29 May – 3 June 2024

R/V Helmer Hanssen

Cruise report

Edited and compiled by Sünne Basedow

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1. Introduction

Sünnje Basedow (UiT)

Vertical migration of zooplankton is the greatest synchronized animal movement on earth! While this knowledge has been established for a few years, there are still many unknowns hidden in this great shift of carbon biomass between surface and deeper water layers. Within the Migratory Crossroads project we aim to develop a comprehensive understanding of the vertical migratory responses of a keystone herbivorous copepod, *C. finmarchicus*, to the cumulative impacts of climate-change-related light, temperature, food availability and visual predation risk, all of which are expected to shift in the future. We are developing a high-resolution mechanistic model for this purpose, and the aim of this cruise is to improve the predictive potential of the model by collecting empirical data with comparable spatial and biological resolution.

Our cruise is accompanied by a field campaign of autonomous platforms, which are collecting data over a longer time period than a cruise allows. A Sailbuoy was set out on the 13th May and was in the vicinity of our study area during the cruise, and collected data until it was recovered on the 26th July. We deployed the Seaglider on 30th May and recovered it on the 2nd of June, it had problems with sampling, see Cruise log.

The study area is the Norwegian Sea off Lofoten-Vesterålen, a highly productive region and known to host high abundances of *C. finmarchicus*. In June, these copepods tend to aggregate at the shelf break, in winter they overwinter in deep areas offshore (Lofoten basin), and our hypothesis is that during seasonal descent they are concentrated in eddies. *C. finmarchicus* is very important for the marine food web, a preferred food of most fishes, e.g. Atlantic cod, herring and saithe.

Our **sampling approach** consisted of:

1. Sample the Hola transect, where the IMR moorings (temporal resolution) are placed and where we have sampled the last years
 - a) MVP w/ LOPC-CTD-F & ship EK60 (18, 38, 120 kHz) transect
 - b) Stations: CTD-F w/ PAR and oxygen sensor, water samples for chl a & nutrients; Multinet for taxonomy; WP2 for biomass and *Calanus* lipid pictures; LOPC-CTD-F, Surface net; Tucker trawl for macrozooplankton, Pelagic trawl for larger predators
2. Locate eddy based on SLA and sample this in detail
 - a) MVP transect
 - b) Stations
3. Other sampling
 - a) Multicorer for analyses of ancient DNA
 - b) 36 hrs station for circadian rhythm studies as part of ClinBluFeed project

2. List of participants

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Photo: Ellen Sofie Griegel

Fig. 1. Cruise participants in the sun on deck.

3. Cruise narrative

Text: Sünnje Basedow (UiT), Photos: Emilia Trudnowska (IOPAN) and Ellen Sofie Griegel (NNKS)

Wednesday, 29.5.: Departure and station 1

We left Tromsø around 09:15 after border control with the police. Sunny and calm when leaving. Fog appeared outside Hekkingen and remained until the end of the day. Unfortunate for obtaining RGB images.

Fig. 2. SLA images from 28th and 29th of May, showing strong eddy south of Hola transect

We arrived at the first station, offshore Hola transect, around 21:30. The station is 2800 m deep. It is too deep for a cast with the Multicorer, unfortunately. There is ca. 2800 m wire available, but strong currents. We tried to set out the Seaglider w/ UVP6 and EK80, but had to abandon it due to too rough sea. Wind is at 10 m s^{-1} . Weather is forecasted to calm a bit, hopefully it will be possible to set out the glider after the station. A low pressure is scheduled for tomorrow evening, by that time we hope to be finished with the MVP transect and at the coastal end of the Hola transect. At Station 1: CTD and Multinet to 1000 m, WP2s for lipids (upper 50 m, 20 CVs) and biomass (100-50, 50-0) size fractionated ($>500 \mu\text{m}$, 180-500 μm). The surface bottle didn't close on the first CTD, a cast for surface water was done later.

A strong eddy is apparent in the SLA images, just south of the Hola transect. This will be exciting to follow over the next day! RGB image with just very little spatial coverage from yesterday due to clouds or fog.

Thursday, 30.5.: Hola transect sampling

Around midnight, we started the MVP line along the Hola transect, at the offshore end. We aimed to go to 800 m to resolve potentially overwintering populations, but had issues with errors (inner sheave) on first profiles. The errors occurred around when the fish was at 500 m depth and therefore we eventually continued sampling just down to 400 m, which worked flawlessly but will of course limit our data to 400 m depth. The sea calmed down somewhat during the night. We finished the MVP line around breakfast.

Fig. 3. Multinet deployment

Station 2 (ca 200 m deep) is on the shelf and close to Bø, and we started sampling it in calm weather. It was a bit overcast in the morning, but sunny in the afternoon, and we may get a good RGB image from today. The wind blows with 8 m s^{-1} , but the sea is calm. We tried to set out the Seaglider but had communication problems, and had to abandon this plan. We will try again at the next station. Also at this station there are many red copepods in Multinet, and the surface net yielded a very nice *Calanus* sample, which was splitted for biomass and taxonomy. In the Tucker trawl there were some ctenophores (*Bolinopsis* and others) and cnidarians and few krill.

Fig. 4. Discussing stations

The eddy close to our line is still strong in the SLA image from 29th May, and we will try to sample it with a MVP transect across and a few stations.

We set out the Seaglider with zodiac in the afternoon at our shelf break station 3. Afterward, in the afternoon, we trawled pelagic at the shelf break (520 m), which resulted in, amongst others, a few myctophids, 4-5 juvenile cod, fish larvae and much krill (mostly *Meganyctiphanes norvegica*, but also several *Thysanoessa* species). Afterwards we continued with our usual program with CTD, Multinet, surface net and WP2s. Finally, we deployed the first Multicorer for ancient DNA sampling. The Seaglider most unfortunately has lost communication to the UVP6, which does not sample as a result.

Friday, 31.5.: Eddy sampling and 36 hr sampling

The weather somewhat deteriorated, so we decided it was too risky to deploy the Moving Vessel Profiler, unfortunately, when we arrived at our starting position for crossing the apparent eddy around 01:00 o'clock. We moved the LOPC over to the ring for vertical sampling at stations and sampled one station at the beginning of our envisioned transect through the eddy, one in the center and then in the morning (09:15) one at the end. Our transect is ca. 50 nautical miles, and during the night we went with only 6 knots due to rough weather.

Fig. 5. SLA (left) and RGB (right) satellite data from May 30th

We started the 36 hrs sampling for Sören's measurements of diurnal variability in gene expression at 10:00, so will finish that 1st June at 22:00. During that time Sören will sample every 4 hrs, but there is

time in between for us to sample other parameters, and we will try to fit some stations into this period. The locality of the 36 hrs sampling is not important, as long as we are in the same area in general, so we can move along our transect during this time. The first sample for Sören (WP2 50-0 m) yielded a very nice, dense sample of strongly pigmented *Calanus*.

The wind has calmed down from 10-12 m s⁻¹ to hardly any wind (1 m s⁻¹) but there is still movement in the sea. The weather forecast is very good.

During sampling station 4 at the southwestern end of eddy, we got the SLA images, which showed that the eddy was still in this area on the 30th May, but has moved slightly. This is good news, and we planned station 5 in the centre of the eddy and station 6 slightly north in the edge of the eddy. The RGB image from the 30th May did yield some visible areas, but not close to the eddy.

The afternoon was very calm, it would have been very good for a MVP transect but is now not possible due to the 36 hr station. At station 4 there were a lot of eggs in a gelatinous layer around in the surface net, and also some in the Multinet. Could they be *Limacina* eggs? Adult *Limacina* was observed in the Multinet and some WP2s. Several blue copepods (Pontelildae) were also observed in the surface net.

Fig. 6. Emilia and the Seaglider

Saturday, 1st June: Eddy sampling and 36 hour sampling continued

During the night, we sampled with the surface net and the Tucker trawl, and both yielded a lot of *Limacina*. In the Tucker trawl there were also several nice *Tomopteris* and fish larvae, amongst other things.

After completing station 5, we moved out of the eddy, towards the shelf edge to sample a Multicorer at around 1800 m, all while sampling the WP2s for the 36 hour sampling in the eddy, but outside of station 5. In the morning, we moved back into the eddy, toward station 6 and sampled a pelagic trawl (420 m) about halfway to our station. *Periphylla periphylla*, myctophids and *Meganctiphanes*, amongst others.

Fig. 7. Students onboard, from left: Anni, Lorenz, Ana and Florence

We arrived at station 6 around 11:15, starting with a CTD to 2000 m. The weather is still very calm, but picked up in the afternoon to 8-9 m s⁻¹. It is overcast with only a few sun glimpses, a RGB image will not be possible. After finishing station 6 successfully, weather conditions were still quite good, 9 m s⁻¹ but not too wavy, and we still have time, so at 19:30 we started a MVP transect through the eddy, from station 6 directly southward, to get a fine spatial resolution of hydrography and zooplankton, which will allow to place our station-based results into a much wider context.

During the weekend we didn't receive SLA nor RGB images, but a map of surface currents from Barentswatch indicated that we did manage to sample the eddy quite precisely, albeit it had moved a bit to the west.

Sunday, 2nd June: Glider pick-up and sampling Malangsdjupet

We finished the MVP transect successfully around 2:30 in the morning, a bit before the shelf (at 800 m depth) because Halibut fishing season had started yesterday and there were a lot of fishing vessels at the shelf break, as usual during this time of the year. After the transect, we headed to the glider, which was ca. 10 hours away, on the way towards Malangsdjupet and arrived there around 12:30. Weather was choppy, winds at 11 m s^{-1} , so it was not possible to recover the glider with the zodiac. The crew managed to capture the Seaglider shortly after it was seen with the crane. All went well and by 13:10 it was safely back on deck, despite the difficult weather. To compare with onshelf (Malangsdjupet), we sampled POM and *Calanus* for stable isotopes at the oceanic Seaglider position ($> 2000 \text{ m}$ depth).

Fig 8. Recovering the Seaglider

In Malangsdjupet the weather was nice and calm. We sampled three stations across Malangsdjupet, with CTD, LOPC and WP2, however, at the 2nd station (station 8), we lost the WP2 due to wrong fixture of the closing mechanism. We finished sampling at 02:00 in the morning of 3rd June, and headed straight to Tromsø thereafter.

4. Research activities

4.1. CTD sampling: Data, chl-a, nutrients, pigments and eDNA

Camila Pompei (DTU Aqua) and the CTD team

Fig. 9. Activity in the wet lab

CTD data were collected by the ship's Seabird CTD (SBE CTD; SBE911plus, SeaBird Scientific, U. S.). Water samples from the lowest layer were taken at each station, these will be analysed using a Guildline Portasal salinometer with the aim to calibrate the salinity sensor. Additional CTD data were collected by the MVP (MVP CTD; Applied Microsystems Ltd.), and the CTD attached to the LOPC frame (LOPC CTD; SBE19plusV2, Seabird Scientific), see section 4.2. All CTD data are stored at UiT.

Water samples were taken from the Niskin bottles attached to the SBE CTD rosette to estimate chlorophyll *a* (Chl-*a*) concentration, nutrients at several depths, and pigment composition at surface.

Nutrients were collected from the bottom (or some deep layers) and at 50, 20, 10, 5, and 0 m. Samples

for Chl-a analysis were taken at 50, 20, 10, 5, 0 and at the Chl fluorescence maxima as shown by the CTD fluorometer. Table 1 shows sampled depths for each station. Chl-a concentration was analyzed onboard while nutrients (UiT) and samples for pigment analysis (IOPAN) were frozen to be processed after the cruise. Preliminary results of the Chl-a samples are shown in Figure 10.

Table 1. Depths and water samples from the CTD

	Depth	Chla	Nutrients	eDNA	HPLC	
Station 1 29/05/24	1000		x	x		
	50	x	x	x		
	20	x	x	x		
	Chlmax	x				
	10	x	x			
	5	x	x	x		
	0	x				x
Station 2 30/05/24	227					
	50	x	x			
	15 (Chlmax)	x				
	20	x	x			
	10	x	x			
	5	x	x			
	0	x	x			x
Station 3 30/05/24	779		x	x		
	50	x	x	x		
	25 (Chlmax)	x				
	20	x	x	x		
	10	x	x			
	5	x	x	x		
	0	x	x			x
Station 4 31/05/24	2563		x	x		
	695			x		
	501		x			
	50	x	x	x		
	20 (Chlmax)	x	x	x		
	10	x	x			
	5	x	x	x		
0	x	x			x	
Station 5 31/05/24	1000		x	x		
	51	x	x	x		
	20 (Chlmax)	x	x	x		
	10	x	x			
	5	x	x	x		
	0	x	x			x
	Station 6 01/06/24	2000		x	x	
1000			x	x		
50		x	x	x		
20 (Chlmax)		x	x	x		
10		x	x			
5		x	x	x		
0		x	x			x

Nutrients

Water samples were taken directly from the Niskin bottles using vinyl gloves. Bottles were rinsed three times with the water from each Niskin bottle before being filled. Just after, samples were stored in the -20 freezer. Samples will be analysed at UiT.

Pigment composition

Samples for HPLC analysis were taken only for the surface layer. 500mL of each sample were filtered using a vacuum pump system and GF/F filters. Next, each filter was folded and placed in aluminum paper, folded, and stored in the -80 freezer. These will be analysed at IOPAN.

Additional notes

At station 1, the Niskin bottle for the surface water did not close. So we had to do an additional CTD cast to collect surface water (about 2:30 hours after the first cast). For station 6, halfway the Chl measurement with the fluorometer, the blanks started to give higher values than normal. We turned off the fluorometer and put the samples back in the cooling room. Two hours later the samples were taken out for half an hour and the fluorometer was turned on again (and also left on for half an hour). The blanks were still high. I suspect that the problem was the change in the batch of cuvettes, as there was no drift in the subsequent blanks. The rest of measurements were taken as normal with the new blank values.

Fig. 10. Chl-a profiles as estimated with the fluorometer.

4.2. LOPC-CTD-F: hydrography, zooplankton size spectra and distributions

Sünnje Basedow and the LOPCi team

The Laser Optical Plankton Counter (LOPC) collects data with a frequency of 2 Hz, and was deployed vertically with a speed of 0.7-0.8 m s⁻¹ at 8 stations (Table 2). This yields data on zooplankton and potentially other particles with high spatial resolution along the vertical axis. Particles can be identified based on their size and transparency (Espinasse et al. 2018). For the Norwegian Sea calibrations against MultiNet and Video Plankton Recorder allow for high certainty in identifying plankton (Gaardsted et al. 2010; Basedow et al. 2013). Preliminary data on hydrography and copepods are seen in Fig. 11.

Table 2. Deployments of the LOPC

Event #	Station	Latitude (deg. N)	Longitude (deg. E)	Bottom depth (m)	Date	Time (UTC)	Sampling
773	Hola transect start	69.386	13.085	2748	29.05.	23:44	Freewheel, 400 m
773	Hola transect end	68.879	24.481	136	30.05.	06:57	
833	Eddy transect start	68.956	11.377	168	01.06.	20:01	Freewheel, 450 m
833	Eddy transect end	68.518	11.379	758	02.06.	00:30	
790	Eddy east	69.315	12.894	2823	30.05.	13:34	1 profile to 1000 m no LOPC data, CTD yes
791	Eddy center	69.063	12.062	2817	31.05.	03:52	1 profile to 1000 m
793	Eddy west / St. 4	68.817	11.254	2597	31.05.	07:15	1 profile to 1000 m
810	St. 5	68.997	11.425	2900	31.05.	20:07	1 profile to 1000 m
828	St. 6	69.272	11.480	2935	01.06.	13:25	1 profile to 1000 m
841	St. 7 Malangsdjupet	68.822	17.474	403	02.06.	19:06	3 profiles to 380 m
845	St. 8	69.760	17.653	442	02.06.	21:13	3 profiles to 434 m
846	St. 9	69.718	17.709	440	02.06.	22:47	3 profiles to 430 m, stopped logging early

The LOPC was also deployed mounted on the Moving Vessel Profiler (MVP; advanced winch, free fall) for collecting data along transects (Table 2). Because of weather conditions the MVP could not be deployed below 450 m. Both the MVP and the profiling frame were equipped with an additional CTD (see section 4.1), which yields data on the physical environment for plankton. The profiling frame was also equipped with a fluorescence sensor (WETLabs EcoFl, Seabird Electronics Inc., USA). All data are stored at UiT.

Fig. 11. Vertical distribution of copepods. Left: supposed eddy center, right: eddy edge.

References

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4.3. Multinet: mesozooplankton species composition, abundance and vertical distribution

Lorenz Schick (UiT) and the zooplankton team

To determine the mesozooplankton community composition, abundance and vertical distribution, we deployed a Multinet (HydroBios Kiel, 180 μm , 0.25 m^2 opening area) at each main station. With each cast of the Multinet, we took five samples of different depth layers. At most Stations, the seafloor was deeper than 1000 m below and the samples were taken at five standard depth strata (1000-500 m, 500-100 m, 100-50 m, 50-20 m and 20-0 m). At station 2 (shelf) and 3 (shelf break), the maximum depth was less than 1000 m and the depth strata were changed accordingly (Table 3). A flow meter in the opening area of the Multinet measured the intake volume of each sample. However, it has been noticed that a rope, attached to the Multinet to move it with a crane, came in contact with the flow meter during the cast and might have tampered with the flow measurement. Each sample was collected in a bottle and fixed in 4% formalin in seawater solution. These samples will be further analyzed at Akvaplan using the Zooscan.

Table 3: Overview of samples taken for Mesozooplankton community analysis with Multinet.

Event #	Station	Latitude (deg. N)	Longitude (deg. E)	bottom depth (m)	Date	Sample time (UTC)	Sample depth from (m)	Sample depth to (m)	Flow (m ³)
768	1	68° 23.36	13° 03.37	2762	29.05.24	20:45	1000	500	155
768	1	68° 23.36	13° 03.37	2762	29.05.24	20:45	500	100	126
768	1	68° 23.36	13° 03.37	2762	29.05.24	20:45	100	50	15
768	1	68° 23.36	13° 03.37	2762	29.05.24	20:45	50	20	9
768	1	68° 23.36	13° 03.37	2762	29.05.24	20:45	20	0	4
775	2	68° 52.81	14° 29.61	233	30.05.24	08:30	220	100	22
775	2	68° 52.81	14° 29.61	233	30.05.24	08:30	100	50	10
775	2	68° 52.81	14° 29.61	233	30.05.24	08:30	50	20	8
775	2	68° 52.81	14° 29.61	233	30.05.24	08:30	20	0	4
784	3	69° 07.74	13° 48.68	954	30.05.24	17:30	750	500	61
784	3	69° 07.74	13° 48.68	954	30.05.24	17:30	500	100	87
784	3	69° 07.74	13° 48.68	954	30.05.24	17:30	100	50	15
784	3	69° 07.74	13° 48.68	954	30.05.24	17:30	50	20	6
784	3	69° 07.74	13° 48.68	954	30.05.24	17:30	20	0	3
799	4	68° 49.05	11° 18.90	2521	31.05.24	11:00	1000	500	103
799	4	68° 49.05	11° 18.90	2521	31.05.24	11:00	500	100	36
799	4	68° 49.05	11° 18.90	2521	31.05.24	11:00	100	50	5
799	4	68° 49.05	11° 18.90	2521	31.05.24	11:00	50	20	2
799	4	68° 49.05	11° 18.90	2521	31.05.24	11:00	20	0	0*
807	5	68° 59.78	11° 25.44	2900	31.05.24	14:58	1000	500	149
807	5	68° 59.78	11° 25.44	2900	31.05.24	14:58	500	100	113
807	5	68° 59.78	11° 25.44	2900	31.05.24	14:58	100	50	13
807	5	68° 59.78	11° 25.44	2900	31.05.24	14:58	50	20	7
807	5	68° 59.78	11° 25.44	2900	31.05.24	14:58	20	0	4
825	6	69° 14.82	11° 28.37	2900	01.06.24	11:55	1000	500	140
825	6	69° 14.82	11° 28.37	2900	01.06.24	11:55	500	100	110
825	6	69° 14.82	11° 28.37	2900	01.06.24	11:55	100	50	14
825	6	69° 14.82	11° 28.37	2900	01.06.24	11:55	50	20	8
825	6	69° 14.82	11° 28.37	2900	01.06.24	11:55	20	0	4

* Inflow meter might have been blocked by a rope

Fig. 12. Multinet sampling

4.4. WP2 net – Zooplankton biomass and lipids

Emilia Trudnowska (IOPAN) and the zooplankton team

4.4.1. Meso zooplankton biomass

To estimate the biomass of the mesozooplankton community a WP2 net (HydroBios Kiel, 180 μm , 0.25 m^2 opening area) was taken from 100-50 and 50-0 water layers (St1-6) and from 50-0/100-0 m (St8-9). Each sample was size fractionated into a 500 μm and 180 μm fraction by pouring it through a 500 and 180 μm sieves. Samples were rinsed with fresh water and placed in pre-weighted filters in numbered dishes and dried at 60°C in the drying oven. The dried samples will be weighed back at UiT.

Table 4. Sampling for mesozooplankton biomass with WP2

Nr	Station	Date	Depth (m)	Size fraction	Dish number	Notes
771	St1	29.05.2024	100-50	500 μm	21	
771	St1	29.05.2024	100-50	180 μm	22	
772	St1	29.05.2024	50-0	500 μm	23	1/8 fraction of sample
772	St1	29.05.2024	50-0	180 μm	24	
776	St2	30.05.2024	Surface, 15min	500 μm	25	1/8 fraction of sample
778	St2	30.05.2024	100-50	500 μm	26	Ctenophores out
778	St2	30.05.2024	100-50	180 μm	26	
779	St2	30.05.2024	50-0	500 μm	28, 29, 30	Ctenophores out
779	St2	30.05.2024	50-0	180 μm	2	
785	St3	30.05.2024	Surface, 15min	500 μm	1, 3	½ fraction of sample
787	St3	30.05.2024	100-50	500 μm	4	
787	St3	30.05.2024	100-50	180 μm	5	
788	St3	30.05.2024	50-0	500 μm	6	½ fraction of sample
788	St3	30.05.2024	50-0	180 μm	7	
801	St4	31.05.2024	Surface, 15min	500 μm	8,16	1/16 fraction of sample
814	St5	31.05.2024	Surface, 15min	500 μm	10,41	1/4 fraction of sample, Ctenophores out
839	St8	02.06.2024	412-100	500 μm	42, 43	
839	St8	02.06.2024	412-100	180 μm	44	
840	St8	02.06.2024	100-0	500 μm	45, 46	Ind. taken for stable isotope analysis
840	St8	02.06.2024	100-0	180 μm	47	
843	St9	02.06.2024	434-100	500 μm	48, 49	½ fraction of sample
843	St9	02.06.2024	434-100	180 μm	50	½ fraction of sample

Fig. 13. Handling zooplankton samples: Elisabeth, Sünnje and Florence in action.

4.4.2. *Calanus* individuals for lipid and pigment content, stable isotope composition

To estimate the lipid content of the most lipid rich and dominating at that time CV life stage of *Calanus*, samples were taken with a WP2 (180 µm mesh size, 0.25 m² opening): from 50 m to surface at stations 1-6. Digital images (lateral view) were taken of 100 *Calanus* individuals per station using a Leica stereomicroscope with a camera (Leica DFC420). The digital images will be used to measure lipid sac area, prosome length and prosome area of specimens using ImageJ, an open source graphics program. Lipid content of individual *Calanus* specimens will be calculated from lipid sac area according to Vogedes et al. (2010). The photographed individuals were then frozen (app 30 pooled together as replicates A,B,C per station) for the HPLC analysis of pigment composition and concentration. The frozen samples will be transported to IOPAN and analyzed there by HPLC.

Fig. 14. Beautiful, pigmented *Calanus* in petri dish (left) and as seen under the microscope.

For the analysis of stable isotope composition, the individuals of CV life stage of *Calanus*, (3 replicates of 10), were carefully picked out at stations 7 and 8 put at filters in and dried at 60°C in the drying oven. The further analysis will be performed at UiT. In general, *Calanus* copepods appeared to be in a good condition and were very red pigmented (Fig. 14).

Table 5. *Calanus* individuals photographed for lipid and frozen for pigment analyses

No	Station	Lat	Lon	Date	Time	Depth	images	replicates
770	St1	69.39	13.07	29.05.2024	22:35	50-0	100	3x30
777	St2	68.88	13.50	30.05.2024	09:24	50-0	100	3x30
786	St3	69.13	13.87	30.05.2024	18:41	50-0	100	3x30
800	St4	68.81	11.32	31.05.2024	12:20	50-0	100	3x30
809	St5	68.99	11.43	31.05.2024	20:10	50-0	100	3x30
830	St6	69.22	11.34	01.06.2024	16:01	50-0	100	3x30
835	St7	69.79	15.09	02.06.2024	11:30	50-0	x	3x10
839	St8	69.82	17.45	02.06.2024	17:52	100-0	x	3x10

4.5. Fiskegruppe – macrozooplankton, pelagic fish, and acoustics

Pierre Priou (APN), Chathumini Kiel (ULB), Kanchana Bandara (APN)

The *Calanus* SIBM model PASCAL v4.0 includes a predation component that requires empirical some tuning and validation. Hence, the Fiskegruppe aimed to (1) identify *Calanus* predator assemblages in different environments (e.g., shelf break/deep basin, surface layer/mesopelagic layer), and (2) document the fine-scale spatio-temporal distribution and, if possible, the circadian migratory dynamics of *Calanus* predators across key transects: the Hola transect and offshore transect targeting a mesoscale eddy. To collect data with a high enough spatio-temporal resolution to be relevant for the model, we used a combination of trawl-based and acoustic sampling. The acoustic data was used to continuously document the presence of sound scattering layers from the ocean's surface down to ca. 1000 m depth, and the trawls were deployed within the observed sound scattering layers to document the species composition and collect samples for further taxonomic and stomach content analyses.

Fig. 15. The fiskegruppe from right to left: Kanchana, Chathumini, Pierre and Sir Tucker moments before disaster ...

4.5.1. Acoustic data collection

We continuously recorded acoustic backscatter with the ship-borne hull-mounted narrowband echosounder (Simrad EK60) at three frequencies: 18 (transducer: ES18-11), 38 (transducer: ES38B), and 120 kHz (transducer: ES120-7). The transducers were mounted on a drop-keel at 6.5 m depth and were pinging simultaneously. Pulse length was set to 1.024 ms, transmitted power was 2000 W for the 18 and 38 kHz transducer and 250 W for the 120 kHz transducer, and the beamwidth was 11 ° for the 18 kHz transducer and 7 ° for the others (Table). The ping rate varied to accommodate for other onboard acoustic instrumentation and changing seafloor bathymetry. For example, the ping rate was 1 Hz in areas where the seafloor was shallower than 700 m and 0.2 Hz in areas where the bathymetry was superior to 2000 m depth. The echosounder was calibrated using the standard sphere method prior to the cruise (Demer et al., 2015).

Table 6. Ship-borne hull-mounted echosounder settings used during the MxR spring 2024 survey.

Transducer	Frequency (kHz)	Pulse length (ms)	Power (W)	Gain (dB)
ES18-11	18	1.024	2000	23.14
ES38B	38	1.024	2000	27.20
ES120-7	120	1.024	250	26.67

We used Echoview 13.1 for the preliminary processing of echosounder data. We removed background noise (signal-to-noise ratio of 10 dB) and the impulse noise generated by other acoustic sensors (De Robertis & Higginbottom, 2007; Ryan et al., 2015).

4.5.2. Trawl sampling and processing

We used two types of trawls to sample pelagic organisms: the Tucker trawl for organisms near the ocean's surface and the Harstad pelagic trawl for the deeper-dwelling animal. Prior to deploying trawls, we identified the depth of the sound scattering layer of interest using the echosounder.

We deployed the Tucker trawl at stations 2 (Holla – shelf), 5 (Offshore – eddy centre), and 6 (Offshore – eddy north) (Table). The Tucker trawl had a 1 m² opening and 1 mm mesh size. It was deployed from the starboard side of the ship using a crane and a boom. An acoustic beacon was installed on top of the mouth opening to monitor the sampling depth. The Tucker trawl was towed horizontally at a depth of 15 m for 17-21 min at a speed of ca. 2 knots. After retrieving the catch, we identified, counted, and measured the biovolume of gelatinous plankton. The rest of the catch were fixed in 4% buffered formalin. Unfortunately, the Tucker trawl got ripped near the cod end during its last deployment at station 6 on June 1st, so these data may only be used qualitatively, not quantitatively.

Fig. 16. Pierre in position for the pelagic trawl

Fig. 17. Handling the

trawl on deck.

We deployed the Harstad pelagic trawl at station 3 (Holla – shelf break), 5, and 6. The trawl had an opening of ca. 18 m x 18 m and an effective height of 9-11 m and effective width of 10-12 m at 3 knots. Acoustic beacons were mounted on top of the mouth of the trawl and on the two doors to continuously monitor the sampling depth and flight characteristics of the trawl. The mesh size of the inner liner of the cod end was 10 mm. Once retrieved, the catch was sorted to the lowest taxonomic level possible. We counted and measured the weight of each taxon. For highly abundant taxon, we weighted a subsample of 50 randomly selected individual and the entire sample to calculate the total abundance. For fish and cephalopod, we also measured the length and weight, and photographed each individual. The length-weight distribution will further be used to parametrize acoustic target strength models to derive the biomass distribution from acoustics.

Table 7. Summary of the deployment times and depth of the Tucker and Harstad pelagic trawls deployments. * The Tucker trawl got ripped along the seam during the deployment at station 6 on June 1st, so these data may only be as qualitative, not quantitative.

Station	St. Nr	Net	Date (dd/mm/yy)	Time surf. start (UTC)	Time at depth start (UTC)	Time at depth stop (UTC)	Time surf. stop (UTC)	Lat start (DD)	Long start (DD)	Lat stop (DD)	Long stop (DD)	Sampling depth (m)
2	780	Tucker	30/05/24	10:05	10:12	10:32	10:34	68.881	14.501	68.874	14.498	15
3	782	Harstad	30/05/24	14:09	14:27	14:50	15:02	69.124	13.946	69.069	13.944	420
5	815	Tucker	31/05/24	22:41	22:44	23:05	23:08	68.987	13.946	69.069	13.944	15
5	822	Harstad	01/06/24	05:24	05:42	06:15	06:27	68.796	11.199	68.844	11.153	420
6	827	Tucker*	01/06/24	12:50	12:54	13:10	13:11	69.281	11.490	69.272	11.478	15
6	829	Harstad	01/06/24	14:55	15:00	15:26	15:31	69.259	11.464	69.231	11.352	450

4.5.3. Preliminary results

The Hola transect crossed over three distinct bathymetric regions: the offshore region where seafloor depth is below 1500 m, the shelf break where seafloor rapidly increase from the deep abyssal plains to the shallow shelf waters, and the shelf where seafloor depth was ca. 200 m depth (Fig. 18).

*Fig. 18. Echogram of volume backscattering strength (S_v in dB re 1 m^2) of the Hola transect when the MVP was deployed at (a) 18 kHz, (b) 38 kHz, and (c) 120 kHz. Orange * indicate the location of the Tucker and Harstad pelagic trawls taken on the Hola transect. The black areas indicate areas where backscatter was removed due to interferences with other acoustic instrumentation or the seafloor.*

Four main scattering features were observed within the Hola transect:

- **Surface sound scattering layer:** located in the upper 50 m of the water column. It was present throughout the entire transect although with lower backscatter on the shelf break (observed at all frequencies) (Fig. 19 a, b, c). We also observed different frequency responses of the surface sound scattering layer in the different areas, e.g., in the offshore area $S_{v18} > S_{v38} > S_{v120}$ whereas on the shelf $S_{v38} > S_{v120} > S_{v18}$ (see Fig. 18).
- **Mid-water schools:** located between 50 and 250 m depth (Fig. 19a). Only observed offshore (Fig. 18).
- **Shelf deep pelagic sound scattering layer:** located between 150 and 250 m depth. It was observed in the shelf and extend into the shelf break but was not seen offshore (Fig. 18).

- **Mesopelagic sound scattering layer:** located between ca. 200 – 700 m depth. It was observed in offshore and shelf break areas. In the shelf break the mesopelagic layer was clearly separated from the shelf deep pelagic sound scattering layer (Fig. 19b). The highest backscatter values for the mesopelagic layer were observed near the seafloor at ca. 300 m depth on the shelf break.

Fig. 19. Echogram of 10 minutes of S_v at 38 kHz in the (a) offshore, (b) shelf break, and (c) shelf area.

Although we did not do in depth taxonomic analyses on the catch from the Tucker trawl (Fig. 20a), there were clearly visible differences in the species composition from the Tucker trawl collected on the shelf and offshore (Fig. 20b, c).

Figure 20. (a) Tucker trawl during deployment at station 2, the acoustic beacon transmitting the depth of the trawl is visible on top of the trawl, (b) catch from station 2 (Holla - shelf), and (c) catch from station 5 (offshore - eddy centre).

The catch from the Harstad pelagic trawl also showed differences between stations. We collected fish larvae from the mesopelagic Harstad trawl, and because we the net cannot close, we assumed that those were collected from surface waters when the net was retrieved. Hence for the following plots we have removed fish larvae from further analyses.

In terms of relative abundance, the nekton community was dominated by the glacier lanternfish (*Benthoosema glaciale*) followed by Mueller's pearlside (*Maurolicus muelleri*) (F).

Fig. 21. Relative abundance (top) and biomass (Bottom) of mesopelagic taxa for each deployment of the Harstad pelagic trawl. Note the different y-axis between the upper and lower panels.

The contribution of Mueller's pearlside was higher at station 3 on the shelf break than offshore (station 5 and 6). For the zooplankton community, euphausiid were the most abundant taxa – mainly *Meganyctiphanes norvegica* – followed by amphipods.

In terms of relative biomass, the small lanternfish and pearlside only had a minor contribution while the larger species like blue whiting (*Micromesistius poutassou*), squid (most likely *Gonatus fabricii*), deepwater redfish (*Sebastes mentella*), spotted barracudina (*Arctozenus risso*), and the helmet jellyfish (*Periphylla periphylla*) were the main contributor to the nekton biomass (Error: Reference source not found). For zooplankton, *Meganyctiphanes norvegica* was the largest contributor to the relative biomass at all stations.

Here are some of the photos taken during the length measurements (Fig. 22). Clear year-size classes were observable in the most abundant taxa.

Fig. 22. Photographs (from top to bottom, left to right) of glacier lanternfish (*Benthosema glaciale*), Mueller's pearlside (*Maurolicus muelleri*), blue whiting (*Micromesistius poutassou*), spotted baracudina (*Arctozenus risso*), deepwater redfish (*Sebastes mentella*), and a cephalopod (possibly *Gonatus fabricii*) caught in the mesopelagic tows.

4.6. Sampling eDNA from sediment and seawater to calibrate plankton indicators of POC flux in the Nordic Seas

Ana Gomes and Tristan Cordier (NORCE)

The particulate organic carbon (POC) flux is a key parameter of the biological carbon pump and the ocean carbon cycle. Whether POC flux will weaken or strengthen in response to global warming remains unclear (Henson et al., 2022). Filling this knowledge gap is crucial as a weaker POC flux would amplify and accelerate ongoing climate change. We aim to contribute to closing this knowledge gap by reconstructing past POC flux from the sediment record and assess its response to past climate transitions (cooling/warming). Our activities are funded through the NFR project BIOCAP: “Reconstructing the biological carbon pump with ancient plankton DNA” and by the Horizon Europe projects ANERIS: OperAtional seNsing life technologies for maRIne ecosystemS and BIOcean5D: Marine biodiversity assessment and prediction across spatial, temporal and human scales. Our primary aim during MXR24 cruise on RV Helmer Hanssen is to collect surface sediment samples (0-1cm, 1-2cm) and seawater samples (plankton) at multiple depths (epipelagic, DCM and meso/bathypelagic) from multiple locations in the Lofoten Basin. We also aim to collect sediment archives (ancient DNA) from 1 or 2 deep stations, by slicing the cores every centimeter. By combining this new eDNA data with publicly available ocean eDNA datasets (for both plankton and sediment samples), we will specifically analyse the plankton DNA signatures that have settled in surface sediments and statistically link those with decadal trends in POC flux that are based on modelling work (e.g. Henson et al., 2011; Nowicki et al., 2022). Using these DNA-based indicators of POC flux in the modern Nordic Seas sediment, we will reconstruct past POC flux using ancient plankton DNA stored in sub-seafloor sediments and analyse its response to past climate transitions.

Cruise objectives:

- 1 – Collect surface sediment and plankton samples to complement an existing eDNA database in the Nordic Seas.
- 2 – Collect sediment archives (i.e. slicing one or two multicores) to reconstruct past POC flux in the Lofoten Basin.

Scientific objectives (post-cruise activities):

- 1 – Develop plankton DNA signatures in surface sediments as POC flux indicators.
- 2 – Reconstruct past POC flux using ancient plankton DNA community profiles.
- 3 – Combine plankton eDNA data from the water column with export estimates based on LOPC / UVP casts on the same stations, to identify potential plankton DNA signatures explaining well the *short-term* variations of POC export in the water column.

4.6.1. Work at sea:

Sediment sampling with Multicorer: A multicorer (MUC, figure 1) built by KC Denmark A/S with two transparent plastic core liners (or tubes) of 60 cm length, an 11 cm outer and 10.6 cm inner diameter, was deployed at stations 3 and 5bis (Table 1). The multicore was equipped with a depth sensor (operational until 1800m depth), attached to a winch rope and lowered through the water column at ca. 1m/s, and 0.5 m/s the last 50m above the seafloor. When the MUC reaches the seafloor, a weight of ~250 kg pushes the cores into the sediments. When retracted from the sediments, arms with spatulas close the bottom and top of each core. The MUC and sediment cores were immediately heaved at ca. 0.7 m/s in order not to disturb the sediment and/or loose material. Once on deck, the bottom and top of each core were secured with plastic end caps. Cores were immediately subsampled for DNA in the “isotope room” of RV Helmer Hanssen (Figure 2), which has been previously cleaned with 10% bleach on all surfaces and benches. We were wearing a full protective and sterile suit, along with gloves, goggles and a face mask. Three sediment subsamples were collected from the 0-1cm and other three subsamples at 1-2 cm. For one core (station 5bis), we sliced every centimeter to collect ancient DNA samples. The samples were placed in a -20°C freezer immediately after subsampling.

Seawater sampling with the CTD

A CTD rosette with 12 Niskin bottles (5L capacity) was used to sample seawater. We collected about 5 liters of water whenever possible at ca. 5, 20, 50, 1000 and 2000 m depth at stations 1, 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7 (Table 8). Seawater was immediately filtered in the isotope room through Sterivex filters (0.22 µm) using a peristaltic pump. Sterivex were labelled and placed in the -20°C freezer right after filtration.

>> **Samples labelling scheme: HH24-StXX-YY-ZZ (XX = Station number, YY = Equipment, ZZ = Replicates or Sediment layers, e.g. 3-4 cm)**

Fig. 23: Multicorer with two tubes. The red blob is a depth sensor.

Fig. 24. Isotope room, where both sediment subsampling and water filtering took place.

4.6.2. Detailed Multicorer methods:

Prior to sampling: make sure that all equipment is cleaned for DNA sampling i.e.

- use nitrile gloves when coming in contact with sediment
- soak end-caps and foam blocks in bleach and rinse with fresh water
- clean all working surfaces with 10% diluted bleach
- pre-label whirlpak bags for subsample collection
- clean spoons and spatulas with bleach and rinse with MilliQ water as needed
- check that all consumables are correctly labelled according to the labelling scheme

1. Core on deck:

- retrieve core liner from multicorer and close the top and bottom with endcaps or foam blocks
- clean exterior of core and label with cast and core number (e.g. MC1-A, MC2-B)
- note station number, cast number, time and date in multicore log sheet
- document observations of core characteristics, including core length in multicore log sheet and take a picture of the core
- failed multicores should always be logged as 'empty' in both the multicore log sheet and the multicore master file
- transport core to laboratory
- dress up with protective gears (sterile blue suit, gloves, goggles, and face mask)

2. Core in laboratory (isotope room):

- place core on extruder, open the lib, siphon off top water from core.
- push the core up until the surface sediment can be easily reached
- remove additional water with pipette
- take photo of core surface and make note of any additional observations
- subsample for DNA using bleach-disinfected spoon avoiding the edges (3 replicates of 0-1 cm and another three replicates of 1-2 cm). In the case of core slicing, push the core 1cm at the time, slice it with spatulas and remove edges (~1 cm) with a butter knife, and collect the slice in a whirlpak bag
- remove subsampled core from extruder and place in a plastic bin for cleaning
- repeat subsampling for remaining cores until all cores have been subsampled
- place all samples in a big plastic bag with labels, and place the bag in the -20°C freezer
- clean the isotope room working surfaces using 10% bleach solution and MilliQ to rinse
- set up consumables for next station
- discard liquid bleach waste in the waste container, NOT down the lab drain

Fig. 25. Filtration for seawater eDNA with a peristaltic pump. On the right-hand side, a Sterivex filter unit is attached and buckets allow measuring the volume filtered.

4.6.3. Detailed CTD methods

1. CTD on deck:

- prior to draining an entire bottle, rinse the tube and the carboy with the sampled seawater (~200mL) by shaking it multiple times in all directions
- drain the 5 liters of water from Niskin bottles into carboys (labelled with depth)

2. In the lab:

- rinse the tubes by pumping approx. ~200-400 mL through them connect the Sterivex filter unit to the Luer-Lok on the tubes (Fig. 25)
- filter 5 liters of seawater (200 rpm)
- make sure the connections are tight and that there is no pressure buildup. If a pressure buildup occurred, filtering should be stopped, and time and how many liters have been filtered should be recorded
- disconnect the Sterivex filter unit from the tube and remove as much of the remaining water as possible using a syringe (e.g. 60 ml) filled with air
- record the volume of water that was filtered by each Sterivex unit
- label the Sterivex unit, place in an individual whirlpack bag with labels
- place all Sterivex of a station in a bigger plastic bag with labels, and place the bag at -20°C.

Table 8: Collected seawater samples from CTD.

Station	Depth (m)	Latitude (DD)	Longitude (DD)	Sampling depths (m)	CTD bottle	Filtration start	Filtration end	Volume filtered (L)	Comments
1 (767 on ship)	2753	69.38730	13.69860	1000	2	23:55	00:57	5	
				50	4	23:08	00:16	5	
				20	6	23:08	00:16	5	
				5	10, 11	23:08	00:29	1.6	
				5	10, 11	23:30	23:52	1.6	
3 (783 on ship)	768	69.10498	13.86082	778	1	19:03	20:50	4.6	Pause for dinner and group photo
				50	3	19:03	20:53	4.7	
				20	7	19:03	20:57	5	
				5	9	20:50	23:12	4.2	Pause for core
4 (795 on ship)	2567	68.82055	11.27150	2566	2	13:20	15:45	4.4	Pause for lunch
				695	3	13:20	15:40	5	
				50	5, 6	13:20	15:48	5	
				20	7, 8	15:46	16:32	3.5	
				5	10, 11	15:42	16:17	2.6	
5 (802 on ship)	2898	68.99798	11.45384	1000	1	17:48	18:47	4.6	No resistance when pulling water from filter
				50	3	17:48	18:50	4.8	
				20	5	17:48	18:53	4.7	
				5	9	18:48	19:25	2.9	
				-	-	-	-	1	Negative control (MilliQ)
6 (824 on ship)	2939	69.26888	11.44328	2000	2	13:00	14:12	5	Pause for group meeting
				1000	3	13:00	14:05	4.7	
				50	5	13:00	14:08	4.9	
				20	7	14:08	15:05	3.2	
				5	10	14:10	16:20	4.2	
7 (834 on ship)	2318	69.79888	15.81170	10	7	14:08	15:05	5	No resistance when pulling water fr. filter
				5	10	14:10	16:20	5	

4.6.4. Plain descriptions of multicorer stations

Station 3 (789, coordinates: 69.12407, 13.89578, depth: 747m): We deployed the multicorer at ca. 10h30pm on 30th of June at station 3, which correspond to the middle of the transect. One tube did not recover sediment (arms with spatulas did not trigger), while the other recovered a ~25 cm core (figure 26). We collected the 0-1 cm and the 1-2 cm.

Fig. 26. Sediment core from station 3.

Fig. 27. Sediment core from station 5.

Station 5bis (817, coordinates: 68.66444, 11.28227, depth 1752m): We steamed towards the shelf break to reach a site with approx. 1800 m depth, and deployed the multicorer at ca. 4h30am on 1st of June. One tube broke on the seafloor while the other recovered a ~40cm core (figure 27). We collected the collected the 0-1 cm and the 1-2 cm, and sliced the rest of the core (down to 33 cm, because the core liner of ~60 cm got stuck to the core extruder bottom, making further extruding of the sediment impossible).

4.6.5. Sampling stations for eDNA

Fig. 28. Map of stations sampled for eDNA Table 9. Collected sediment samples.

Station	Depth (m)	Latitude (DD)	Longitude (DD)	Length of sediment core (cm)	Core depth (cm)	Comments
3 (789 on ship)	747	69.12407	13.89578	20	0-1	1 core/1 failed. only surface sediments collected
					1-2	
5B (817 on ship)	1752	68.66444	11.28227	35	Every centimeter up to 33 cm	1 core/1 failed. brown sediment until 12-13 cm where it became greyish and some samples were more sandyish (12-13 cm and 16-17 cm) and others more clayish (14-15 cm)

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4.7. *Calanus finmarchicus* diel molecular rhythmicity in the Norwegian Sea

Sören Häfker (AWI)

As part of the CliN-BluFeed project (leader: Lionel Camus, Akvaplan-niva), time series for the molecular analysis of diel rhythmicity of *Calanus finmarchicus* under natural conditions. All samplings were conducted around 69°5 N, 11°2 E.

As a first aspect, copepods were collected for gene expression analysis from surface waters over a period of 36 hours, with samples collected via vertical WP2-net hauls from 50 m depth to the surface. Starting on May 31st at 10:00, samples were collected in 4 hour intervals, resulting in a total of 10 time points (last time point at June 1st at 22:00). At each time point, animals were fixed as bulk samples in RNAlater stabilizing solution (3 replicates per time point), stored at 4°C for 24 hours and then transferred to -20°C for long-term storage.

After transport to the AWI, bulk samples will be sorted for *C. finmarchicus* CV stages, which will then be used for the generation of a diel transcriptome that describes the entirety of gene expression changes within the animals over the course of the 24 hour cycle. The gain information will be used to determine the rhythmicity of the copepods' circadian clock as well as other metabolic and neuronal process. This will grant insight into the internal processes that regulate vertical positioning including diel including diel vertical migration behavior and feeding rhythms.

As a second aspect, copepods were collected for *in situ* staining investigations at four time points and in 2 different depths, again via vertical WP2-net hauls. Hauls were conducted at 12:00, 18:00, 00:00, and 06:00, each time from 100 m to 50 m depth, and from 50 m to the surface. At each time point, bulk samples of *C. finmarchicus* (2 replicates per time point and depth) were first fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde solution followed by washing steps in phosphate-buffered saline with 0.1% Tween20. Afterwards, bulk samples were stepwise transferred to 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% methanol, before being stored at -20°C long-term.

After transport to the AWI, the samples will be sorted for *C. finmarchicus* CV stages and will be used for staining protocols to visualize the regions where specific genes are expressed in the copepod body and where corresponding proteins are localized. This will be done via hybridization chain reaction (HCR) and antibody staining, respectively. Focusing on the genes and proteins that make up the copepods circadian clock as well as potential light receptor genes, these investigations will help to understand, which clock components co-localize and therefore have the potential to interact on the molecular levels. Localization of light receptors can further help to identify signaling pathways that convey information about the external day/night light cycle to the body regions harboring the circadian clock.

Fig. 29. R/V Helmer Hanssen back in Tromsø after a successful cruise

5. Presentations

During evenings several scientific presentations were given. Below Camila S. Pompei is presenting.

6. Event log

Event #	Station	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°E)	Bottom depth (m)	Date (UTC)	Time (UTC)	Gear	Sampling depth (m)	Sample type	Preservation
767	St. 1	69.39	13.07	2753	29.05.24	0:82	CTD w/ F, PAR, Oxy.	750,50,20,15,10,5,0	Nutrients, Chl, eDNA	Frozen, Data
768	St. 1	69.4	13.04	2760	29.05.24	0:86	Multinet 180 µm	1000-500-100-50-20-0	ZP taxonomy	Formaldehyde
769	St. 1	69.416	13.025	2769	29.05.24	22:20	CTD w/ F, PAR, Oxy.	surface	Nutrients, Chl, HPLC	Frozen, Data
770	St. 1	69.391	13.073	2753	29.05.24	22:45	WP2 180 µm	50-0	<i>Calanus</i> lipids, HPLC	Pictures, Frozen
771	St. 1	69.390	13.059	2756	29.05.24	23:02	WP2 180 µm	100-50	Biomass	Dried
772	St. 1	69.466	13.049	2756	29.05.24	23:16	WP2 180 µm	50-0	Biomass	Dried
773	Hola transect	69.391	13.066	2755	29.05.24	23:44	MVP w/ LOPC,CTD,F	400-0	ZP size spectra, Environ.	Data
774	St. 2	68.877	14.487	249	30.05.24	07:45	CTD w/ F, PAR, Oxy.	bottom,50,25,20,10,5,0	Nutr.,Chl,HPLC,eDNA	Frozen, Data
775	St. 2	68.883	14.497	233	30.05.24	08:14	Multinet 180 µm	220-100-50-20-0	ZP taxonomy	Formaldehyde
776	St. 2	68.891	14.510	227	30.05.24	08:46	Surface net 500 µm	15 min at surface	Biomass, Taxonomy	Dried, Formaldehyde
777	St. 2	68.883	14.503	229	30.05.24	09:24	WP2 180 µm	50-0	<i>Calanus</i> lipids, HPLC	Pictures, Frozen
778	St. 2	68.884	14.502	230	30.05.24	09:28	WP2 180 µm	100-50	Biomass	Dried
779	St. 2	68.887	14.502	231	30.05.24	09:44	WP2 180 µm	50-0	Biomass	Dried
780	St. 2	68.882	14.503	229	30.05.24	10:07	Tucker trawl	20 min at 15 m	Biovolume, Taxonomy	Data, Formaldehyde release
781	St. 3	69.115	13.906	684	30.05.24	13:27	Seaglider w/ EK80			
782	St. 3	69.105	13.945	687	30.05.24	14:11	Pelagic trawl	520	Fish+MacroZP size, Fish	Data, Formaldehyde
783	St. 3	69.105	13.861	769	30.05.24	16:07	CTD w/ F, PAR, Oxy.	778,50,42,20,10,5,0	Nutr.,Chl,HPLC,eDNA	Frozen, Data
784	St. 3	69.129	13.810	954	30.05.24	17:00	Multinet 180 µm	750-500-100-50-20-0	ZP taxonomy	Formaldehyde
785	St. 3	69.126	13.852	915	30.05.24	18:10	Surface net 500 µm	15 min at surface	Biomass, Taxonomy	Dried, Formaldehyde
786	St. 3	69.125	13.874	775	30.05.24	18:41	WP2 180 µm	50-0	<i>Calanus</i> lipids, HPLC	Pictures, Frozen
787	St. 3	69.126	13.880	756	30.05.24	18:49	WP2 180 µm	100-50	Biomass	Dried
788	St. 3	69.123	13.897	846	30.05.24	19:07	WP2 180 µm	50-0	Biomass	Dried
789	St. 3	69.124	13.896	748	30.05.24	19:28	Multicorer	748	ancient DNA	Frozen
790	Eddy east	69.315	12.894	2823	30.05.24	23:34	LOPC w/ CTD, F	1000	ZP size spectra, Environ.	Data
791	Eddy center	69.063	12.062	2817	31.05.24	03:52	LOPC w/ CTD, F	1000	ZP size spectra, Environ.	Data
792	St. 4	68.816	11.245	2596	31.05.24	06:58	CTD w/ F, PAR, Oxy.	bottom,500,50,20,10,5,0	Nutr.,Chl,HPLC,eDNA	Frozen, Data
793	St. 4	68.817	11.254	2597	31.05.24	07:15	LOPC w/ CTD, F	1000	ZP size spectra, Environ.	Data
794	St. 4	68.820	11.267	2609	31.05.24	08:02	WP2 180 µm			
795	St. 4	68.821	11.271	2610	31.05.24	08:16	WP2 180 µm			
796	St. 4	68.820	11.305	2537	31.05.24	10:04	WP2 180 µm			
797	St. 4	68.820	11.307	2532	31.05.24	10:17	WP2 180 µm			

798	St. 4	68.819	11.312	2524	31.05.24	10:36	WP2 180 µm				
799	St. 4	68.818	11.313	2520	31.05.24	10:43	Multinet 180 µm	1000-500-100-50-20-0	ZP taxonomy	Formaldehyde	
800	St. 4	68.813	11.324	2483	31.05.24	12:14	WP2 180 µm	50-0	<i>Calanus</i> lipids, HPLC	Pictures, Frozen	
801	St. 4	68.811	11.326	2477	31.05.24	12:29	Surface net 500 µm	15 min at surface	Biomass, Taxonomy	Dried, Formaldehyde	
802	St. 5	68.998	11.454	2897	31.05.24	14:15	CTD w/ F, PAR, Oxy.	1000,50,20,10,5,0	Nutr.,Chl,HPLC,eDNA	Frozen, Data	
803	St. 5	68.998	11.443	2899	31.05.24	16:07	WP2 180 µm				
804	St. 5	68.997	11.438	2899	31.05.24	16:23	WP2 180 µm				
805	St. 5	68.996	11.430	2899	31.05.24	16:39	WP2 180 µm				
806	St. 5	68.996	11.424	2900	31.05.24	16:48	WP2 180 µm				
807	St. 5	68.995	11.423	2900	31.05.24	16:58	Multinet 180 µm	1000-500-100-50-20-0	ZP taxonomy	Formaldehyde	
808	St. 5	68.997	11.430	2900	31.05.24	19:59	WP2 180 µm				
809	St. 5	68.996	11.428	2900	31.05.24	20:07	WP2 180 µm	50-0	<i>Calanus</i> lipids, HPLC	Pictures, Frozen	
810	St. 5	68.997	11.425	2900	31.05.24	20:16	LOPC w/ CTD, F	1000	ZP size spectra, Environ.	Data	
811	St. 5	69.001	11.405	2905	31.05.24	21:44	WP2 180 µm				
812	St. 5	69.003	11.403	2906	31.05.24	22:02	WP2 180 µm				
813	St. 5	69.003	11.402	2906	31.05.24	22:08	WP2 180 µm				
814	St. 5	69.002	11.400	2907	31.05.24	22:18	Surface net 500 µm	15 min at surface	Biomass, Taxonomy	Dried, Formaldehyde	
815	St. 5	69.000	11.384	2908	31.05.24	22:40	Tucker trawl	20 min at 15 m	Biovolume, Taxonomy	Data, Formaldehyde	
816	St. 5	68.996	11.362	2913	01.06.24	00:01	WP2 180 µm				
817	1800 m	68.664	11.282	1752	01.06.24	02:25	Multicorer	1752	ancient DNA	Frozen	
818	Eddy	68.700	11.298	1948	01.06.24	03:59	WP2 180 µm				
819	Eddy	68.705	11.300	1961	01.06.24	04:14	WP2 180 µm				
820	Eddy	68.705	11.301	1964	01.06.24	04:24	WP2 180 µm				
821	Eddy	68.707	11.302	1968	01.06.24	04:35	WP2 180 µm				
822	Eddy	68.808	11.185	2668	01.06.24	05:35	Pelagic trawl	420	Fish+MacroZP size, Fish Data, Formaldehyde		
823	Eddy	69.087	11.315	2936	01.06.24	08:01	WP2 180 µm	50-0		RNAlater	
824	St. 6	69.436	11.443	2938	01.06.24	09:20	CTD w/ F, PAR, Oxy.	2000,1000,50,20,10,5,0	Nutr.,Chl,HPLC,eDNA	Frozen, Data	
825	St. 6	69.274	11.459	2937	01.06.24	10:55	Multinet 180 µm	1000-500-100-50-20-0	ZP taxonomy	Formaldehyde	
826	St. 6	69.283	11.482	2936	01.06.24	12:29	WP2 180 µm	50-0		RNAlater	
827	St. 6	69.282	11.491	2935	01.06.24	12:50	Tucker trawl		Biovolume, Taxonomy	Data, Formaldehyde	
828	St. 6	69.272	11.480	2935	01.06.24	13:25	LOPC w/ CTD, F	1000	ZP size spectra, Environ.	Data	
829	St. 6	69.248	11.418	2939	01.06.24	14:55	Pelagic trawl	450	Fish+MacroZP size, Fish Data, Formaldehyde		
830	St. 6	69.224	11.504	2942	01.06.24	16:01	WP2 180 µm	50-0		RNAlater	
831	Eddy transect	69.216	11.379	2939	01.06.24	17:02	MVP w/ LOPC,CTD,F	450-0	ZP size spectra, Environ.	Data	
832	Eddy	68.960	11.379	2893	01.06.24	19:48	WP2 180 µm	50-0		RNAlater	
833	Eddy transect	68.956	11.377	2895	01.06.24	20:01	MVP w/ LOPC,CTD,F	450-0	ZP size spectra, Environ.	Data	

834	Glider station	69.799	15.081	2318	02.06.24	11:14	CTD w/ F, PAR, Oxy.	10	POM stable isotopes	Dried
835	Glider station	69.794	15.089	2304	02.06.24	11:29	WP2 180 µm	50-0	<i>Calanus</i> stable isotopes	Dried
836	St. 7 Malangs.	69.817	17.421	407	02.06.24	16:27	CTD w/ F, PAR, Oxy.		POM, stable isotopes	Dried
837	St. 7	69.817	17.429	416	02.06.24	16:45	WP2 180 µm	bottom-0	Taxonomy	
838	St. 7	69.817	17.438	417	02.06.24	17:26	WP2 180 µm	417-100	cod end fell off	
839	St. 7	69.822	17.454	422	02.06.24	17:52	WP2 180 µm	412-100		
840	St. 7	69.825	17.466	397	02.06.24	18:23	WP2 180 µm			
841	St. 7	69.822	17.474	403	02.06.24	19:06	LOPC w/ CTD, F	3 profiles to 380 m	ZP size spectra, Environ.	Data
842	St. 8	69.759	17.635	438	02.06.24	19:59	CTD w/ F, PAR, Oxy.		POM	
843	St. 8	69.760	17.641	446	02.06.24	20:13	WP2 180 µm	bottom-100	Biomass, Taxonomy	Dried, Formaldehyde
844	St. 8	69.760	17.650	444	02.06.24	20:55	WP2 180 µm	lost WP2!		
845	St. 8	69.760	17.653	442	02.06.24	21:13	LOPC w/ CTD, F	3 profiles to 434 m	ZP size spectra, Environ.	Data
846	St. 9	69.718	17.709	440	02.06.24	22:47	LOPC w/ CTD, F	3 profiles to 430 m	ZP size spectra, Environ.	Data
